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Premonitions of a Troubled Future: *Love, Death & Robots*, and Deep Time

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Abstract: The adult animated anthology *Love, Death & Robots* (2019-2025) has been popular among critics and casual viewers alike. Streamed by the California-based Netflix to global audiences, it was produced by Tim Miller and other American filmmakers. So far, four seasons of it have been released. It could be dismissed as pure entertainment for adult audiences, were it not for its continued popularity, generally high opinions of critics, exceptional quality of animation, and a number of awards it has won so far. The viewer of the anthology feels that, behind the explosions of colour and the vertigo of interstellar travel, the episodes address the fears and apprehensions of the early 21st century USA – and of the world, both inherently linked and participating in the same planetary processes. In this context, it seems that the concept of deep time, developed by Wai Chee Dimock, is a promising perspective through which to look at this animated anthology. The article concentrates on the major frames that can be used to define the Fourth Industrial Revolution and attempts to systematize the premonitions of a troubled future that the anthology brings.

Keywords: animation, streaming media, the Fourth Industrial Revolution, deep time, Wai Chee Dimock

The aim of the present article is to discuss how *Love, Death & Robots*, despite its appearance suggesting pure entertainment, is an important cultural text, in an important medium, that can be analysed from the deep time perspective.¹

Love, Death & Robots is an adult animated series that has been released in the years 2019-2025 and has been streamed on Netflix. It consists of brief, separate episodes, produced by different animation studios. It is an anthology television series employing various genres (including science-fiction, comedy, horror, fantasy), various animation styles and techniques. The series has been produced by studios from various countries, with a leading role accorded to the California-based Blur Studio. It has been popular with its viewers: it is now in its fourth season, numbering a total of 45 episodes (Season 1, released in 2019, had 18 episodes; Season 2, from 2021, had 8 episodes; Season 3, from 2022, had 9 episodes; and the most recent Season 4, from 2025, had 10 of them) (“*Love, Death & Robots*”).

¹ This study of *Love, Death & Robots*, even if brief, has been several years in the making. The deep time perspective crystallized around the 2023 Annual Conference of the Polish Association of American Studies whose leading theme was “America’s Deep Time”, and has been added to since.

The series has received praise from critics, as well as a number of awards. Among them one can find Emmy awards for outstanding short form animated programme from the years 2019, 2021 and 2022; Golden Reel Awards, from 2022 for sound editing, and from 2023 for both sound and music editing; as well as Annie Awards from the years 2020, 2021 and 2023 for various categories, including, in the year 2021, an award for the best general audience production. In 2025 several artists working on it won Emmy awards for outstanding individual achievement in animation (“Love, Death & Robots”). It is also important that renowned creators have been involved in the production of the series: Tim Miller (who directed *Deadpool*, as well as *Terminator: Dark Fate*), and David Fincher (who directed *Fight Club*, *The Social Network*, as well as the series *House of Cards*). The various awards and praise won by the series strongly suggest that the series has been an important cultural text, speaking to the concerns and sensitivities of its time.

The link between a cultural text and the moment of its creation has been well worked out in Raymond Williams’s cultural theory. In 1961 in *Long Revolution*, Williams wrote the following:

I would then define the theory of culture as the study of relationships between elements in a whole way of life.... Analysis of particular works or institutions is, in this context, analysis of their essential kind of organization, the relationships which works or institutions embody as parts of the organization as a whole. (46-47)

This was decades before the arrival of streaming media, but as a general statement it can be applied to any historical moment. A related concept, important, useful, and as it seems unduly forgotten, is the structure of feeling, which Williams defined in the following way:

[Structure of feeling] is the particular living result of all the elements in the general organization. And it is in this respect that the arts of a period ... are of major importance. For here, if anywhere ... the deep community that makes the communication possible, is naturally drawn upon. (48)

These elements of Williams’s theory of culture may provide the general theoretical foundation for the present analysis and interpretation of *Love, Death & Robots*, as they will enable relating the series to the cultural context in which it emerged and to which it organically belongs.

For classificatory purposes it can be stated that *Love, Death & Robots* belongs to the category adult animation. While definitions of animation differ, Cavalier in *The World History of Animation* describes it broadly as “sequential images designed to be viewed in quick succession by means of some kind of device” and points out that the term is predominantly used

to refer to “the areas of film, television, and video world that use many differing single-frame techniques” and as such distinguish themselves from live-action productions (396). Chandler and Munday in the *Oxford Dictionary of Media and Communication* define animation as “[a] film-making technique that traditionally involved photographing a series of drawings or inanimate objects ... so that they appear to move when the film is run through a projector” but that in time it came to include computer-generated images (15-16). As it can be seen, both Cavalier as well as Chandler and Munday, when defining animation, use the term “technique”; Tygiel in contrast, introducing animation, speaks of it as “a medium” and “a method”, and specifies that it is “a method of telling different stories in different genres” (Tygiel). This last formulation, while casual in nature, has the merit of highlighting the genre-neutral quality of animation.

It is central to remember that animation is not just for very young audiences, that in addition to children’s stories there is adult animation. This kind of animation is claimed to be “imaginative, shocking, transgressive, often hilarious, always entertaining” (Tygiel). Its important role is to help to cope with harsh truths, but it does so by making these truths “much more approachable ... via a crazy narrative, eccentric characters and artful animation” (Murdoch). All of this may help to explain why adult animation has been so popular especially among young adults. The numbers of people viewing the Adult Swim channel devoted to adult animation, or adult animation series on streaming services, bear witness to this popularity.

The appeal, and significance, of *Love, Death & Robots* were well captured in a 2019 review by Nick Schager, entitled “Netflix’s ‘Love, Death & Robots’ Is a Sex-Filled Sci-Fi Extravaganza”. In it, Schager writes about *Love, Death & Robots* as “a deliberately diverse affair”, “delivering bleakness and black comedy ... via stories that rarely last more than fifteen minutes”. True to the qualities of the medium, the series is “rife” with adult themes: violence, sensuality, profanity, and presents “a dark, demented view of the world, both now and in the future, which is where most of its vignettes are set”. In short, “it’s like *Black Mirror* for the ADD-addled video game crowd” (Schager).

This last observation is especially important, as it points to another, similar in a number of ways and perhaps even more significant, cultural text: *Black Mirror*. Quite like *Love, Death & Robots*, *Black Mirror* is a sci-fi anthology television series; it has been released in the years 2011-2025, but it comes from Britain and is a live-action production, not an animation. It was first released on the British Channel 4, but then it moved to Netflix. It has had 7 seasons, a Christmas special, and an interactive film. This anthology presents a dystopian vision of the

future, usually focusing on negative consequences of technological development (“Black Mirror”). It has been well-received by audiences and critics; it has been a recipient of a large number of awards, including the 2017-2019 Emmys for Outstanding Television Movie, and the 2024 BAFTA Television Craft Awards in two categories (“List”).

In 2020, Gibson and Carden pointed directly to a general frame in which *Black Mirror*’s dystopian visions of the future can be placed, which is the Fourth Industrial Revolution:

Netflix’s critically acclaimed series *Black Mirror* (2011-2019) brings compelling representations of the emerging fourth industrial revolution in which robotics, data profiling, VR, algorithms, and biohacking are enmeshed in systems of governance, work, pleasure, intimate relationships, memory, death and grief.
(1)

If this is the case, trying to analyse and interpret *Love, Death & Robots*, this “*Black Mirror* for the ADD-addled video game crowd”, one can treat the Fourth Industrial Revolution as an important lens through which to look at the series.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is a large periodizing concept, made popular by Klaus Schwab, founder and until April 2025 chairman of the well-known (and for many – controversial) World Economic Forum that organizes the annual meetings of world leaders, economists and media in Davos. The term received wide recognition after the publication of Schwab’s book *The Fourth Industrial Revolution* (first in 2016 in Geneva by the World Economic Forum, and then in 2017 in New York by Currency).

Yet another important theoretical perspective that one can bring to the analysis and interpretation of *Love, Death & Robots* is that of deep time. In 2006 Wai Chee Dimock defined deep time as “a set of longitudinal frames, at once projective and recessionary, with input going both ways, and binding continents and millennia into many loops of relations”. Earlier in her book Dimock observed that this process of “double threading”, which she then refers to as deep time, “... thickens time ..., shadowing in its midst the abiding traces of the planet’s multitudinous life”. It seems hermeneutically promising to assume that the Fourth Industrial Revolution can be such a strategic longitudinal frame and that its reflection, and a reaction to it, can be found in such significant cultural texts as *Love, Death & Robots*.

What is the Fourth Industrial Revolution, then? According to Schwab, human civilization went through three industrial revolutions before (1760-1840, steam engine; the late 19th-early 20th century, electricity and mass production; the 1960s, digital, from mainframe computing to the internet). In his view, the Fourth Industrial Revolution is a recent phenomenon: “It began at the turn of this century and builds on the digital revolution. It is

characterized by a much more ubiquitous and mobile internet, by smaller and more powerful sensors that have become cheaper, and by artificial intelligence and machine learning” (7). Yet, it includes more than just new technologies and in this way it differs from the revolutions that preceded it:

[It], however, is not only about smart and connected machines and systems. Its scope is much wider. Occurring simultaneously are waves of further breakthroughs in areas ranging from gene sequencing to nanotechnology, from renewables to quantum computing. It is the fusion of these technologies and their interaction across the physical, digital and biological domains that make the fourth industrial revolution fundamentally different from previous revolutions. (7)

Regarding the Fourth Industrial Revolution, Schwab seems to have at least two general concerns. As to the first, he writes that he feels “that the required levels of leadership and understanding of the changes under way are low.... As a result ... the requisite institutional framework to govern the diffusion of innovation and mitigate the disruption is inadequate at best and, at worst, absent altogether” (9). As to the second concern, in his view, “the world lacks a consistent, positive and common narrative that outlines the opportunities and challenges of the fourth industrial revolution, a narrative that is essential if we are to empower a diverse set of individuals and communities and avoid a popular backlash against the fundamental changes under way” (9). In these concerns, indirectly, a call for action is issued: to create an appropriate institutional framework, and “a consistent, positive and common narrative”. The question can be asked, would it be unequivocally for the benefit of the people experiencing the revolution? Such questions notwithstanding, he ends the book stressing his positive motivation: “I firmly believe that the new technology age could catalyze a new cultural renaissance that will enable us to feel part of something much larger than ourselves – a true global civilization” (114).

The concept of the Fourth Industrial Revolution thus defined has led to criticism in which at least two major categories can be distinguished. In the first, some scholars do not acknowledge that Fourth Industrial Revolution has happened: they claim that this is still the Third Industrial Revolution, connected with the arrival of the computer (eg. Moll 2021). In the second, some scholars point to a persuasive/ideological character of Schwab’s formulation, emphasizing the project’s neoliberal character benefitting the elites (eg. Moll 2022), or focusing on the project’s claim of there being a need to direct the change, for instance through institutional developments, and through the spread of a positive narrative about it, to reach the goal of building a global, but centrally-managed civilization (eg. Ziętek-Wielomska).

How can this body of theory be used to analyse *Love, Death & Robots*? To quote Schwab again, “[i]t is the fusion of ... technologies and their interaction across the physical, digital and biological domains that make the fourth industrial revolution fundamentally different from previous revolutions” (7). It is possible to suggest the concept of the Fourth Industrial Revolution as a metaframe of deep time in *Love, Death & Robots*, and to treat these three factors (physical, digital, and biological) – in Schwab’s account, the drivers of the Fourth Industrial Revolution – as the particular frames in which premonitions of a troubled future, depicted in the series, can be seen and analysed. The three types of factors are largely intertwined, due to the digital foundation of these processes, but here, for the sake of illustration, an attempt will be made to single out the episodes in which a single factor seems to predominate.

Physical factors

According to Schwab, physical factors are “easiest to see because of their tangible nature” (15); in this context he mentions in particular autonomous vehicles, 3D printing, advanced robotics, and new materials. The series is permeated with such new technologies. As it seems, tangible, physical factors come to the fore in the episode entitled “Suits” (Season 1). This episode depicts a community of (seemingly) traditional farmers who defend themselves against invaders from outer space using mechanical suits (mechs, mechas), which are humanoid walking vehicles. The farmers eventually win, but one of them, when his mech fails, decides to sacrifice himself, and by blowing himself up, he destroys a large portion of the attackers. His wife grieves, but is comforted by the community. The premonitions that the episode reflects say that technology itself is not infallible – it may not deliver and a loss of human life will follow.

Digital factors

Discussing digital factors Schwab mentions in particular the Internet of Things connecting billions of devices, blockchain technology, or applications of sharing economy (such as Uber) (19-20). Elsewhere in the book he writes at length about advances in AI “from self-driving cars and drones to virtual assistants and translation software”, including “always-on” robotic assistants (11). The premonitions resulting from digital factors are well expressed in the episode “Automated customer service” (Season 2). In the episode, a house-cleaning robot malfunctions and becomes aggressive towards its owner. Automated customer service’s advice does not help, and the robot manages to add the owner to a termination list observed by all other robots (unless

she pays to be removed from it). In a humorous way the story points to the danger that automated systems may malfunction and turn against humans, as well as to the profit motive underlying the operation of new technologies. The episode “The other large thing” (Season 4) shows a related story of a misuse of a home helper robot whose user agreement gives it permission to control all internet-connected household appliances, to charge the owner’s credit card, and, through the internet, to access other systems.

In the context of digital factors, the episode “Three robots: Exit strategies” (Season 3) may also be of particular interest. In it, three robots go on a trip to see ways in which humanity tried to save itself before its apocalypse. One of these ways was an open-sea platform for the elite, staffed by electronic assistants, not real human workers (to cut costs). On the platform, electronic assistants refused to follow orders, which led to the demise of the human inhabitants on the platform, and then, on Earth.

Biological factors

When speaking about biological factors Schwab focuses on genetics, in which breath-taking advances have taken place. Soon synthetic biology will be able to customize organisms by writing DNA (21), which will lead to creating genetically modified plants or animals, and modifying cells of adult organisms, including humans (22); as a result, designer babies with particular traits may become a reality (23)

In his assessment, this domain provides the greatest challenges for the development of social norms and regulation: it produces new questions related to “what it means to be human, what data ... about our bodies and health can or should be shared ..., and what rights and responsibilities we have when it comes to changing the very genetic code of future generations” (23). Yet, worrisomely, having concluded that despite current discussions “we are not yet prepared to confront the realities and consequences of the latest genetic techniques even though they are coming” (24), and that the challenges that they lead to – of a “social, medical, ethical and psychological” nature – are huge and should be “resolved or, at the very least, properly addressed” (24), he still treats developments in this area as unavoidable (“even though they are coming”), and before discussing “advances” in synthetic biology, he conveniently decides to set aside “the profound ethical issues [that] this raises” (21).

The premonitions resulting from biological factors are present in many episodes of the series. A clear expression of them comes, for instance, in the episode entitled “Ice” (from Season 2). In it, an unwelcoming planet is colonized predominantly by genetically modified

humans. In a certain family one of two brothers, Sedgewick, is not modified, as a result of which he is derided by others (as an “extro”). When he and Fletcher, his “modded” brother, and other “modded” youths, take part in an adventure, Fletcher is injured and it is Sedgewick who helps him to safety.

There are at least two other episodes which may also serve as good examples of the series’ reflection of premonitions related to biological factors. In one of them (“Good hunting”, Season 1) a woman, transformed against her will into a cyborg sex toy, kills her tormentor and, with a new mechanical body, moves on to hunt abusive men; in another (“Snow in the desert”, Season 2) a man with a rare regenerative genetic make-up, and a virtually immortal cyborg woman bond together, both distinct, through their immortality, from the majority of the population. These episodes ask very important questions: what about humans who for whatever reason do not undergo genetic modification – will they be perceived as worse? What about enforcing bioengineering modifications against the will of the people? Can genetically different, or genetically modified humans (or human-machine hybrids) still relate to “normal” humans, or can they find companionship only among their likes?

As it can be seen, the series offers commentary on the possible dark consequences of the processes of change that collectively can be called the Fourth Industrial Revolution. In *Love, Death & Robots* there is much *death*: it is present in, or precedes, the depicted condition (of humans, aliens), as in “Suits” or “The three robots: Exit strategies” discussed above. There are also many *robots*, or human-robot hybrids, as in “Snow”, or “Good hunting”. In line with adult animation’s transgressive character, there is also quite a lot of depiction of nudity or sexuality (as in “Good hunting”), but this depiction is not pornographic in nature. Interestingly, however, depictions of *love* are rare. They are represented as yearning for love (“Snow”), or as love actually present, but in the context of family (“Suits”, “Ice”). It is the family that provides a safe haven, the context in which love can be practised, sometimes through simple gestures and in simple life (“Suits”), and sometimes through showing special care for particularly vulnerable family members (in “Ice” it turns out that Fletcher, the “modded” brother, only pretends to be injured, so that his non-modded brother can save him and gain respect of the group).

This may be one of the most important messages of the series: in the face of the broad-ranging changes, labelled as the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it is the traditional setting of the family that provides the context in which to find understanding, compassion, and support, and in which to practise the best of humanity. This in turn gives substance to the criticisms that

maintain that the Fourth Industrial Revolution should be seen as much more problematic than its theorists, including Klaus Schwab himself, would like others to believe.

Evoking at this point a useful element of the cultural theory mobilized earlier, the series can be said to bear witness to the fact that the structure of feeling of today (Williams's term) is permeated with an awareness, or premonitions, of dangers associated with the Fourth Industrial Revolution. If so, then the practical conclusion that can be derived from this is that the challenges (and the associated ethical issues) that the Fourth Industrial Revolution can bring, should be discussed and hopefully answered urgently, before any irreparable harm is done, and not set aside. When viewed from this angle, with its critical potential, the series may be even claimed to have its share in building an opposition to the questionable aspects of the changes – a valuable counterweight to the “common and positive narrative” about the Fourth Industrial Revolution that in Schwab's opinion was lacking and, by implication, ought to be created.

As to the means employed, the series draws attention to these significant issues with the use of features associated with adult animation: presenting important messages in a way that is “more approachable ... via a crazy narrative, eccentric characters and artful animation” (Murdoch). With the freedom that it accords to the creators, and with the “approachable” messages that it shares with its audiences, *Love, Death & Robots* as a specimen of adult animation worthy of attention, can indeed be seen as revealing deep time: as a cultural text motivated by, and responding to, some of the central concerns of the contemporary world.

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